

Assessment of Shelf-lives of Black Pepper and Small Cardamom Cookies by Metal Oxide based Electronic Nose using Spoilage Index

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Abstract

E-nose technology has been successfully employed in determination of rancidity in nutraceutical-rich drop cookies. The cookies were formulated with extracts obtained by supercritical carbon dioxide extractions and post-extraction sample matrices of black pepper and small cardamom. Rancidity in cookies was estimated by comparing the odor profiles of stored cookies with the profiles of deliberately rancid cookies (training sets), using e-nose. PCA plots along with spoilage indices obtained from Mahalanobis distances calculated from e-nose responses revealed that, the extracts and post-extraction sample matrices of these spices performed as natural antioxidants in preventing rancidity in cookies. Both the extracts enhanced the shelf lives of cookies by at least 120 days; post-extraction matrices of black pepper and small cardamom enhanced the same by 80 and 40 days, respectively. These findings were further affirmed by biochemical analyses and linear regression equations were generated for prediction of FFA content, PV and MDA values from the spoilage indices of each type of cookie. Thus, spoilage indices can circumvent the requirement of conducting cumbersome biochemical assays for estimation of rancidity in cookies. Similar applications of e-nose technology and spoilage indices can be envisaged for other bakery products also.

Keywords Black pepper · Small cardamom · α -amylase-assisted SC-CO₂ extraction · Cookies · E-nose analysis · Mahalanobis distance

Introduction

Cookies are one of the major bakery products consumed globally (Pratima and Yadave, 2000), which have the propensity of undergoing rancidity. This investigation has endeavored to mitigate

this problem by designing antioxidant-rich nutraceutical cookies using extracts of black pepper (dried berries of *Piper nigrum* L.) and small cardamom [dried fruits of *Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton.] obtained by supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) extraction. However, the assessment of shelf-lives of these antioxidant-fortified cookies is a challenge. Presence of high amount of fat impedes titrimetric and other methods of analysis of rancidity and accurate assessment of effect of antioxidant in enhancement of shelf-life of cookies by any direct technique. Sensory analysis plays a crucial role in defining shelf-life of cookies, but it is usually time-consuming and is characterized by poor reproducibility of results. Moreover, sensory evaluation has some limitations owing to the subjectivity of human panels, which may give conflicting results.

To circumvent this limitation, Chatterjee et al. (2012) have employed state-of-the-art technology of electronic nose (e-nose) for analysis of rancid-spoilage of cookies formulated with spray dried SC-CO₂ extract of clove buds and assessment of their shelf lives. This technique minimizes the difficulties of sensory evaluation by mimicking the human olfactory system and provides rapid monitoring of flavor and/or aroma of food products. In the present investigation, metal oxide semiconductor (MOS)-based electronic nose and vision (ENOVISION, an e-nose, developed by Center for Development of Advanced Computing (C-DAC), Kolkata, India) has been employed to assess rancidity in black pepper and small cardamom cookies.

Two dimensional principal component analysis (PCA) has reportedly been carried out to study the changes in aroma of cookies during storage. Chatterjee et al. (2014) have used PCA-based method using ENOVISION for distinct discrimination of ‘rancid’ (deliberately made) and ‘sample’ (stored for 200 days) cookies prepared with SC-CO₂ extract of clove bud. These authors have reported a discrimination index of 99.21% using the said e-nose. However, to accurately distinct between fresh and rancid cookies, graphical representation of their odor profiles alone is

insufficient. Moreover, PCA plots are unable to predict the storage period of a cookie from its e-nose response. Therefore, it is necessary to generate a 'numeric value', based on e-nose responses, which would be an indicator/index of rancidity in cookies. This index would be more reproducible and robust for assessment of rancidity in cookies with storage.

Therefore, in the present investigation, we have applied Mahalanobis distance method for analysis of the e-nose data, which uses distance matrix to develop an index of rancidity. This Mahalanobis distance thus obtained would be considered as the value for 'spoilage index' (SI) for each type of cookie. Subsequently, regression equations would be generated to predict the PV values, FFA and MDA contents of cookies using the value of Mahalanobis distance. To the best of our knowledge, design of cookies using SC-CO₂ extracts of black pepper and small cardamom and assessment of rancidity in cookies by Mahalanobis distance from e-nose responses have erstwhile not been attempted by researchers.

Besides employing the above-mentioned extracts, the residual sample matrices of black pepper and small cardamom, post SC-CO₂ extraction, have also been utilized in designing cookies, allowing complete utilization of these expensive spices. Therefore, the specific objectives of this study were: designing cookies with extracts obtained from SC-CO₂ extractions and using post-extraction residual sample matrices of black pepper and small cardamom; evaluation of nutraceutical properties of the designer cookies and assessment of their shelf-lives by e-nose technology using PCA and Mahalanobis distance.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Malabar Garbled black pepper and seeds of Alleppey Green small cardamom were procured from Spices Board, Cochin, India. Specialty chemicals such as α -amylase from *Bacillus licheniformis*

(lyophilized powder, 500-1500 units/mg protein, 93-100% SDS-PAGE), piperine (97% pure), 1,8-cineole (99% pure), 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), sodium nitroprusside and gallic acid were procured from M/s Sigma, India. Silica gel 60 (F₂₅₄) coated Al plates, Folin-Ciocalteu's phenol reagent (FCR), ethanol, toluene, ethyl acetate, *n*-hexane and sodium carbonate were procured from M/s E-Merck, Mumbai, India. Food grade CO₂ was procured from BOC India Ltd., Kolkata, India. All chemicals used in this work were of AR grade.

α -amylase-assisted SC-CO₂ Extractions of Piperine-rich Black Pepper Extract and 1,8-cineole-rich Small Cardamom Extract

α -amylase-assisted SC-CO₂ extractions of piperine-rich black pepper extract and 1,8-cineole-rich small cardamom extract were conducted in a laboratory scale model 'SCF Green Technology SPE-ED SFE 2' of Applied Separations, Allentown, USA. 20 g of ground ($d_p=0.42\pm 0.02$ mm) black pepper was mixed with lyophilized α -amylase (in optimized ratio of 5000:1) and subjected to SC-CO₂ extractions. α -amylase-assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of piperine-rich extract from black pepper was conducted at the pre-optimized conditions of 300 bar pressure, 60 °C temperature and 135 min extraction time with 2 L/min flow rate of gaseous CO₂ (Dutta and Bhattacharjee 2015). 1,8-cineole-rich small cardamom extract was obtained from α -amylase-assisted SC-CO₂ extraction conducted at pre-optimized conditions of 200 bar pressure, 50 °C temperature and 135 min extraction time with 2 L/min flow rate of gaseous CO₂ from 20 g of ground ($d_p=0.42\pm 0.02$ mm) small cardamom (Dutta and Bhattacharjee 2016). Both extracts were stored in amber colored screw capped glass vials and the post-extraction residual sample matrices were packed in Al foils and placed in Ziploc pouches (M/s Johnson, India). The extracts and the post-extraction sample matrices were flushed with nitrogen and stored at 4 ± 1 °C, until application.

Design of Antioxidant-rich Nutraceutical Cookies

Black pepper and small cardamom extracts obtained from α -amylase-assisted SC-CO₂ extractions and their respective post-extraction sample matrices were utilized in formulation of antioxidant-rich drop cookies. Cookies were prepared in accordance with the method described by Chatterjee et al. (2012) (Table 1), with few modifications. The cookies were baked on a greased pan at 190 °C for 13 min inside a rotary rack convection baking oven (Model CMHS-108, Chanmag Bakery Machine Co. Ltd., New Taipei city, Taiwan). Three sets of cookies were prepared: control, i.e., without addition of any antioxidant (C), cookie fortified with extracts (E_B for black pepper cookie and E_S for small cardamom cookie) and cookies fortified with post-extraction sample matrices (R_B for black pepper cookie and R_S for small cardamom cookie) (Fig. 1).

The quantity of each extract employed in formulation of cookies was 0.3 g/100 g dough weight (wet basis, i.e., w.b). The antioxidant properties of cookies prepared with 0.2 g extract/100 g dough weight (w.b) was significantly (P=0.0290) lower than that of the cookies with 0.3 g extract/100 g dough weight (w.b); whereas, a pungent taste was sensed in the cookies prepared with 0.4 g extract/100 g dough weight (w.b). Therefore, an extract concentration of 0.3 g/100 g dough weight (w.b) was selected for formulation of both E_B and E_S cookie samples.

For cookies formulated with post-extraction residual sample matrices, quantity of sample matrix added to the dough was 5 g/100 g dough weight (w.b), for either matrix. For these cookies, sample matrices less than 5 g/100 g (w.b) did not show appreciable antioxidant potencies; whereas, concentrations greater than this, rendered the cookies waxy (adjudged by an oily mouthfeel in sensory evaluation). Therefore, concentration of the residual sample matrices in both R_B and R_S cookies was fixed at 5 g/100 g dough weight (w.b).

Cookies formulated without and with antioxidants were packed in Al foil, placed in Ziploc pouches, flushed with nitrogen and stored at room temperature (23±2 °C) for shelf-life study of 200 days, in accordance with the procedure described by Chatterjee et al. (2014).

Characterization of Cookies

Physical properties of cookies

Diameter (D), thickness (T), weight and spread ratio (SR=D/T) of cookies were determined by AACC method 10-50D (Arun et al. 2015). Hardness of cookies was assessed by a texture analyzer (TA.XT Express, Stable Micro Systems, England), equipped with a 10 kg load cell. The cookies were penetrated with a cylinder probe (SMSP/5, diameter 5 mm) to a distance of 15 mm at a trigger force of 5 g. The peak breaking forces (N) of cookies were estimated using the force-in-compression mode of analyzer. The texture analyzer was set at a return-to-start cycle, with a pre-test speed of 1.0 mm/s, test speed of 0.5 mm/s and post-test speed of 10 mm/s.

Color of cookies were assessed by Hunter Lab colorimeter (Konica Minolta Inc., Japan) at a 10° inclination from the light source and reported as L*, a* and b* values. L* value indicates lightness, with 100 for white and 0 for black; a* value indicates redness when positive and greenness when negative; b* value indicates yellowness when positive and blueness when negative. The color co-ordinates of these cookies were calibrated against a standard white plate. Chroma values and hue angles were calculated using standard equations (Eqs. 1-2) (Chatterjee and Bhattacharjee 2014).

$$\text{Chroma} = (a^{*2} + b^{*2})^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Hue angle} = \tan^{-1}(b^*/a^*) \quad (2)$$

Phytochemical properties of cookies

Determination of phytochemical properties and piperine (for black pepper) and 1,8-cineole (for small cardamom) contents of cookies was conducted from the methanolic extracts of the cookies (Sakac et al. 2010). Antioxidant potency and total phenolic content of cookies were estimated for every set of cookies, according to the methods reported by Dutta and Bhattacharjee (2016).

Piperine contents of black pepper cookies (both E_B and R_B) were estimated by high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC), according to the method reported by Dutta and Bhattacharjee (2016) and expressed as mg piperine/g cookie (d.w.b., i.e., dry weight basis). In brief, 20 μ L of each sample was spotted as bands on pre-coated silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ Al plates (200 mm \times 100 mm) using Camag Linomat 5 (M/s Camag, Switzerland). The chromatogram was developed in the solvent system toluene: ethyl acetate:: 7:3 at 25 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C in a Twin Trough Chamber (200 mm \times 100 mm). The plates were scanned with Camag TLC Scanner 3 at 337 nm using a Deuterium lamp at a scanning speed of 20 mm/s. Piperine contents of cookies were determined from the standard curve prepared using standard piperine ($R_f=0.3\pm 0.01$).

1,8-cineole contents of E_S and R_S cookies were determined by HPTLC analysis and expressed as mg 1,8-cineole/g cookie (d.w.b), in accordance with the method reported by Ghosh et al. (2015). For this analysis, the chromatogram was developed in the solvent system *n*-hexane: ethyl acetate:: 6:1 at 25 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C. The plates were sprayed with a saturated solution of antimony chloride (III) and kept at 100 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 min in a hot air oven. The amount of 1,8-cineole present in the cookies was determined from the standard curve prepared with standard 1,8-cineole ($R_f=0.58\pm 0.01$, at 500 nm).

Determination of Shelf-life of Cookies

Shelf-life study of cookies was conducted by assessing their rancidity profiles using both e-nose analysis and conventional biochemical assays, at an interval of 20 days for a storage period of 200 days.

Electronic Nose System for Detection of Rancidity in Cookies

Rancidity in the cookies was detected by e-nose system (ENOVISION, C-DAC, Kolkata, India). The system consists of 8 broadly tuned (non-specific) metal oxide gas sensors, each of these sensors consists of a metal oxide film such as tin oxide that respond to a wide range of volatile organic compounds (VOCs).

The array of sensors is exposed to VOCs through suitable odor handling and delivery systems that ensure constant exposure rate to each of the sensors. The VOCs from samples undergo redox reactions at the sensor surfaces, resulting in an increase of conductivities across the sensors and the corresponding changes in voltages are recorded. These signals from the sensor array are conditioned and processed through suitable circuitry and delivered to an intelligent pattern recognition engine for analysis. A mini air compressor is used to maintain requisite airflow. Three solenoid valves are used to route the airflow to the sample holder and the sensor array (Fig. 2). A blower is used to reinforce air evacuation during purging (Bhattacharyya et al. 2008).

In this investigation, optimization of process parameters such as batch size and granularity of cookies, heating time, time for headspace generation, sampling and purging time were ascertained from preliminary trials. The e-nose was calibrated using different batches of powdered cookies and optimization of the parameters was conducted based on the maximum response of the sensors. Based on findings of preliminary trials, 50 g of ground cookie powder ($d_p=0.50\pm 0.02$ mm) was charged into a 100 mL vial and heated by a 50 W miniature halogen lamp for 450 s at 50 ± 2 °C. The headspace was allowed to generate for 30 s to ensure adequate concentration of VOCs. Sampling time for sensors was kept constant at 50 s. Post sensing, fresh air was purged for 300 s at 5 mL/s flow rate, to enable the sensors to return to their baseline values.

For detection of rancidity in cookies, the e-nose system was trained with deliberately-made rancid cookies: C cookie for training (TC), E_B cookie for training (TE_B), R_B cookie for training (TR_B), E_S cookie for training (TE_S) and R_S cookie for training (TR_S) in accordance with the method reported by Chatterjee et al. (2012).

The rancid cookies were prepared by keeping the freshly prepared C, E_B, R_B, E_S and R_S cookies in an accelerated rancidity chamber under UV light to promote oxidation of cookies at constant temperature of 40±2 °C. On completion of the ageing treatment, the samples were removed from the rancidity chamber at predetermined intervals (mentioned later), flushed with nitrogen and stored in a 'conservation chamber' to maintain the final rancidity stage.

Selection of E-nose Sensor for Determination of Rancidity in Cookies

The responses of the e-nose sensors for all types of cookies were determined according to the method reported by Chatterjee et al. (2014). For each sample, $\Delta R/R$ value was calculated for every sensor, which is the change in signals from the metal oxide sensors due to the VOCs of cookies on day 'd', with respect to the signals generated for freshly prepared cookies. In order to select the sensors most sensitive towards VOCs of rancidity in control, black pepper and small cardamom cookies, e-nose responses for TC, TE_B, TR_B, TE_S and TR_S cookies were plotted against storage time. The sensors which showed the highest and stable responses were selected as the 'best sensors' for each type (control, black pepper and small cardamom) of cookies. Analysis of rancidity in cookies was conducted at an interval of 20 days for 200 days.

Biochemical Assays for Determination of Rancidity in Cookies

Biochemical assays such as determination of free fatty acid (FFA) content, peroxide value (PV) and thiobarbituric acid value (TBA) were conducted to estimate rancidity in cookies. These FFA, PV and TBA were considered as 'conventional rancidity parameters' in this study. They were

estimated according to the methods reported by Chatterjee et al. (2014) and expressed as % oleic acid, meq/kg of cookies and mmol malonaldehyde/g cookies, respectively.

Statistical Analyses

In this investigation, PCA was performed by XLSTAT 2014.5.03 (Microsoft Corporation, USA). Distances among the data points were used as the basis of identification of differences in odor profiles of cookies. Evaluation of these distances was conducted by the Mahalanobis distance method.

In brief, the Mahalanobis distance evaluates the distance between two data points by assigning different weights or importance factors to the features of data points in the set. In the present study, estimation of Mahalanobis distance was conducted using MATLAB 7.6.0. (R2008a) (Maths-Work, USA). Regression equations were generated using STATISTICA Software version 8.0 (StatSoft, OK) to predict the PV values, FFA contents and MDA contents of cookies as functions of Mahalanobis distances. Significant differences between means were determined by Duncan's multiple-range test using IBM SPSS Statistics software version 20 (IBM, USA). A P value of 0.05 was used to verify the significance of all tests.

Results and Discussion

Characterization of Cookies

Physical properties of cookies

Similar values of diameter, thickness and weight of control, black pepper and small cardamom cookies indicated no adverse change of these parameters of cookies on fortification with SC-CO₂ extracts and post-extraction sample matrices of black pepper and small cardamom (Table 2). The spread factor obtained for the cookies were in the range of 4.52-4.69. Abdel-Samie et al. (2010)

have obtained similar dimensions (4.03-4.26 cm diameter, 0.65-0.74 cm thickness) and spread factor (5.43-6.54) for cookies prepared with cumin and ginger powders. Hardness of the cookies was in the range of 48-52 N (Table 2), which was similar to the hardness reported by Jacob and Leelavathi (2007) for cookies prepared with hydrogenated fat.

From the L^* , a^* , b^* values of cookies, it has been found that, application of extracts in cookies enhanced the brightness of the same (Table 2). The L^* values of both E_B and E_S cookies (64.79 ± 0.70 and 63.88 ± 0.60 , respectively) were enhanced significantly ($P=0.0007$ and $P=0.0012$, respectively) over that of the C cookies (60.88 ± 0.20). On the other hand, cookies with post-extraction sample matrices had significantly ($P<0.05$) decreased redness and yellowness for R_B ($a^*=5.69 \pm 0.29$ and $b^*=20.79 \pm 0.46$) and R_S ($a^*=4.59 \pm 0.15$ and $b^*=18.57 \pm 0.30$) cookies compared to C cookies ($a^*=9.61 \pm 0.06$ and $b^*=26.15 \pm 0.04$).

Phytochemical Properties of Cookies

From the phytochemical properties, the antioxidant potency of C cookies decreased by 6.62 times (from 14.38 to 95.30 mg/mL) after 200 days of storage (Fig. 3a) and its total phenolic content was depleted after 80 days of storage (Fig. 3b). For black pepper cookies, antioxidant potencies and total phenolic contents of E_B cookies decreased by 1.04 times (from 1.08 to 1.12 mg/mL) and 1.64 times (from 22.23 to 13.55 μg gallic acid equivalent/g cookie), respectively; whereas, 1.38 times (from 1.25 to 1.72 mg/mL) decrease of antioxidant potency and 2.92 times (from 10.43 to 3.56 μg gallic acid equivalent/g cookie) decrease of total phenolic content was obtained for R_B cookies (Fig. 4a-b).

The decrease in antioxidant potencies and total phenolic contents in small cardamom cookies during storage period of 200 days was higher than that of the black pepper cookies. For small cardamom cookies, antioxidant potencies of E_S and R_S cookies decreased by 2.07 times (from 0.28

to 0.58 mg/mL) and 9.94 times (from 0.85 to 8.45 mg/mL) respectively, after 200 days of storage. The total phenolic content decreased by 1.47 times (51.64 to 35.20 μg gallic acid equivalent/g cookie) for E_S cookies and 5.22 times (36.73 to 7.03 μg gallic acid equivalent/g cookie) for R_S cookies during storage period of 0 to 200 days (Fig. 4a-b). This result indicated that formulation of cookies with black pepper protected the nutraceutical value of cookies more than that observed for small cardamom.

Piperine content of fresh E_B cookies was 101.56 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry cookie which decreased insignificantly ($P=0.0705$) during the storage period (piperine content of 200 day-stored cookies was 98.23 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry cookie) (Fig. 5a). For E_S cookies, 1,8-cineole content of fresh cookies was 1.161 mg/g dry cookie, which degraded to 0.633 mg/g dry cookie ($P=0.0000$) over the storage period of 200 days (Fig. 5b). Piperine contents of fresh R_B cookies and 1,8-cineole contents of fresh R_S cookies (0.084 mg/g dry cookie and 0.504 mg/g dry cookie, respectively) were significantly ($P=0.0000$) low, compared to those of the E_B and E_S cookies (Fig. 5a-b). After 200 days of storage piperine content of R_B cookies was 0.079 mg/g dry cookie (Fig. 5a), whereas, after 80 days of storage, 1,8-cineole could not be detected in R_S cookies any longer (Fig. 5b). However, compared to C cookies, R_B and R_S cookies had significantly higher antioxidant potencies ($P=0.0000$) and total phenolic contents ($P=0.0000$) (Fig. 4a-b) even after 200 days.

These observations indicated that addition of extracts and post-extraction sample matrices of black pepper and small cardamom increased the nutraceutical properties of cookies. Black pepper cookies exhibited higher nutraceutical properties and minimizes the degradation of the same compared to small cardamom cookies throughout the storage period of 200 days. Therefore, it can be concluded that, black pepper extract and post-extraction sample matrix prevented the nutraceutical properties of cookies better than small cardamom.

Selection of E-nose Sensors for Analysis of Rancidity in Cookies

E-nose sensor which showed highest response with minimum variation in detection of rancidity in black pepper cookies (TE_B and TR_B) was TGS2610 followed by TGS2600 and TGS2611 (Fig. 6a-b). Therefore, these three sensors were selected for assessment of rancidity in black pepper cookies, similarly, for both small cardamom and control cookies, TGS823, TGS832 and TGS2600 were selected (Fig. 6c-e).

E-nose System for Assessment of Rancidity in Cookies

Analysis of rancidity in cookies using PCA-based odor maps for each type of cookie indicated the relative positions of the data point of each cookie of the sample set with respect to those of the training set (Fig. 7). The PCA plot of control cookies revealed that, odor profile of 80 day-stored cookies was similar to that of the fresh control cookies; however, the data points of C cookies for storage of 100 days and above were present in the same quadrant along with the cluster of TC cookies (Fig. 7a). This result attested that C cookies were non-rancid up to 80 days.

In PCA plots for both E_B and E_S cookies, 200 day-stored cookies formed a separate cluster, distant from that of TE_B and TE_S , respectively, indicating that cookies formulated with SC-CO₂ extracts of black pepper and small cardamom averted rancidity in cookies for at least 200 days (Fig. 7b-c). PCA further revealed that data points of R_B were in the same quadrant of TR_B from 180 days, indicating rancidity in R_B cookies from 180 days (Fig. 7d). Similarly, from PCA plot, shelf-life of R_S cookies was found to be 120 days (Fig. 7e).

Therefore, PCA plots of black pepper and small cardamom cookies revealed that, enzyme-assisted SC-CO₂ extracts prevented rancidity and enhanced the shelf lives of both cookies by at

least 120 days; whereas, post-extraction sample matrix of both spices enhanced the shelf lives of cookies by at least 40 and 80 days, respectively.

Determination of Mahalanobis Distance between Fresh Cookies and Stored Cookies

SI was generated for each type of cookies (SI_C for control cookie, SI_{EB} for cookie with black pepper extract, SI_{RB} for cookie with residual black pepper matrix, SI_{ES} for cookie with small cardamom extract, SI_{RS} for cookie with residual small cardamom matrix) using Mahalanobis distance method (Table 3).

The SI_C of 100 day-stored C cookies (15.6680) was significantly higher ($P=0.0000$) than 1 day-rancid TC cookies (14.9807), which revealed that 100 day-stored C cookies became rancid (Table 3). This finding was in agreement with the data of PCA plots, wherein the data points of 100 day-stored C cookies was within the cluster of rancid cookies (Fig. 7a). The SI values of 200 day-stored E_B (20.5565) and E_S (15.2153) cookies suggested that both values were significantly ($P=0.0000$) distant from that of rancid cookies (55.8281 and 30.0843, respectively) (Table 3). For R_B and R_S cookies, SI values indicated that, R_B cookies became rancid from 180 days (SI of 180 day-stored R_B and 1 day-rancid TR_B were 41.7037 and 40.1788, respectively) and rancidity in R_S cookies was from 140 days onwards (SI values of 140 day-stored R_S and 1 day-rancid TR_S were 15.9160 and 16.9719, respectively) (Table 3).

The SI values validated the observations of the PCA plots of cookies that, SC-CO₂ extracts enhanced the shelf lives of black pepper and small cardamom cookies by at least 120 days, whereas post-extraction matrices enhanced the same by 80 days in R_B and 40 days in R_S cookies. Moreover, these indices established numeric values which can precisely and accurately distinguish between fresh and rancid cookies.

Determination of Conventional Rancidity Parameters of Cookies

Comparing the values of biochemical assays (FFA, PV and TBA) of stored cookies with deliberately rancid cookies, it was found that C cookies remained non-rancid at least for 80 days, after which its conventional rancidity parameters were found to be similar with those of TC cookies (Fig. 8). Similarly, R_B and R_S cookies remained non-rancid at least for 160 and 120 days, respectively; but for E_B and E_S cookies, no such trend was observed and it remained non-rancid till the end of the storage period of 200 days (Fig. 8). Therefore, values of biochemical assays were in good agreement with the shelf-lives assessed by e-nose analyses.

Correlation between the Rancidity Parameters of Cookies Determined by E-nose Analyses and Biochemical Assays

Since the data from e-nose analyses were well-correlated with the biochemical assays, linear regression equations were generated by multiple regression analyses to predict the FFA, PV and TBA values of cookies (individually for each cookie type), as a function of their SI values (Table 4). Good correlation coefficients (*r*) of the equations (Eqs. 3-17) suggest that these equations can be used to predict the conventional rancidity parameters of cookies from their SI values obtained from e-nose data.

For C cookies, conventional rancidity parameters, i.e., values of FFA, PV and MDA have been calculated from e-nose responses of the cookies using Eqs. 3, 4 and 5, respectively (Table 4). For 1 day-stored TC cookies, the values of FFA, PV and MDA were 1.040% oleic acid, 10.110 mEq/kg cookie and 2.559 mmol/g cookie respectively (Fig. 8a-c). C cookies having similar or higher values of FFA, PV and MDA can be considered as rancid samples. Similarly, for E_B and E_S cookies, conventional rancidity parameters have been calculated using Eqs. 6, 7, 8 and Eqs. 9, 10, 11, respectively (Table 4). For 1 day-stored TE_B cookies, values of FFA, PV and MDA were 1.040%

oleic acid, 9.560 mEq/kg cookie and 1.209 mmol/g cookie and those of TE_S cookies were 1.080% oleic acid, 9.560 mEq/kg cookie and 1.209 mmol/g cookie, respectively (Fig. 8a-c).

For R_B and R_S cookies, FFA, PV and MDA values were calculated from Eqs. 12, 13, 14 and Eqs. 15, 16, 17, respectively (Table 4). The values of the rancidity parameters for 1 day-stored TR_B and TR_S cookies were 1.080% oleic acid (FFA), 9.560 mEq/kg cookie (PV) and 1.839 mmol/g cookie (MDA) and 1.300% oleic acid (FFA), 9.560 mEq/kg cookie (PV) and 1.814 mmol/g cookie (MDA) respectively (Fig. 8a-c). Values of FFA, PV and MDA of cookies calculated from their corresponding SI value can be used to estimate the rancidity in cookies, i.e. cookies having similar or higher values of FFA, PV and MDA compared to their corresponding rancid cookies can be considered as rancid samples. Therefore, e-nose technology can be effectively employed to detect rancidity in cookies designed with black pepper and small cardamom avoiding the need to conduct biochemical assays, making the assessment more accurate and accelerated.

Conclusion

E-nose technology (having 8 MOS sensors) has been successfully employed for detection of rancidity in drop cookies designed with extracts obtained from α -amylase-assisted SC-CO₂ extractions of black pepper and small cardamom and residual sample matrices post-extraction. PCA plots and Mahalanobis distances obtained from e-nose responses of cookies, revealed that SC-CO₂ extracts of black pepper and small cardamom enhanced shelf lives of cookies by at least 120 days; while the post-extraction residual sample matrices of black pepper and small cardamom, enhanced the same by 80 and 40 days, respectively.

Mahalanobis distance calculated for each type of cookie was considered as the 'spoilage index', which is a numeric value that can rapidly and accurately predict the rancidity and hence the shelf life of cookies. The results of e-nose analyses were in good agreement with the results obtained by

standard biochemical assays. Finally, regression equations generated using the biochemical indices (FFA content, PV value and MDA content for each type of cookie) and the e-nose responses (spoilage indices) would allow prediction of the former values, foregoing routine biochemical assays. Similar methodology using spoilage indices can also be employed for accurate assessment of rancidity in other bakery and confectionary products.

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Figure

Fig. 1 Different sets of cookies designed (a) control (C), (b) cookie fortified with black pepper extract (E_B), (c) cookie fortified with small cardamom extract (E_S), (d) cookie fortified with post-extraction residual sample matrix of black pepper (R_B), (e) cookie fortified with post-extraction residual sample matrix of small cardamom (R_S)

Fig. 2

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of e-nose system of ENOVISION (Chatterjee et al. 2014)

Fig. 3 Changes in phytochemical properties of control (C) cookies with storage days

Fig. 4 Changes in phytochemical properties of black pepper (E_B and R_B) and small cardamom (E_S and R_S) cookies with storage days (a) antioxidant potency (IC₅₀ value), (b) total phenolic content

Fig. 5 Changes in piperine and 1,8-cineole contents of black pepper and small cardamom cookies with storage days (a) piperine content of black pepper cookies (E_B and R_B), (b) 1,8-cineole content of small cardamom cookies (E_S and R_S)

Fig. 6 Selection of e-nose sensors based on responses obtained for deliberately-made rancid cookies (a) TE_B, (b) TR_B, (c) TE_S, (d) TR_S, (e) TC

Fig. 7 PCA plots of (a) C cookies, (b) E_B cookies, (c) E_S cookies, (d) R_B cookies, (e) R_S cookies

Fig. 8 Results of biochemical assays of all types of cookies during the storage period of 200 days along with deliberately made rancid cookies (a) FFA content, (b) PV value, (c) MDA content

Table 1 Formulation of drop cookies

Ingredients	% (wet basis, w/w of dough weight)
Wheat flour	50.0
Powder sugar	20.0
Hydrogenated vegetable fat	20.0
Butter	2.0
Milk powder	2.0
Ammonium bicarbonate	0.8
Table salt	0.6
Sodium bicarbonate	0.4
Lecithin	0.3
Water	8.0

Table 2 Physical properties of cookies

Sample	Diameter* (cm)	Thickness* (cm)	Spread ratio	Weight* (g)	Hardness* (N)	L*	a*	b*	Chroma	Hue angle (°)
C	5.74±0.02 ^a	1.23±0.05 ^a	4.67 ^a	25.20±0.20 ^a	49.67±0.30 ^b	60.88±0.20 ^b	9.61±0.06 ^d	26.15±0.10 ^c	27.86±0.10 ^c	69.82±0.12 ^a
E _B	5.65±0.03 ^a	1.25±0.04 ^a	4.52 ^a	25.10±0.30 ^a	48.35±0.50 ^a	64.79±0.70 ^d	9.70±0.05 ^d	27.09±0.14 ^d	28.77±0.15 ^d	70.30±0.14 ^b
E _S	5.70±0.04 ^a	1.24±0.03 ^a	4.59 ^a	25.20±0.10 ^a	49.55±0.30 ^b	63.74±0.60 ^c	8.53±0.04 ^c	28.23±0.16 ^c	29.49±0.16 ^c	73.19±0.17 ^c
R _B	5.72±0.03 ^a	1.22±0.04 ^a	4.69 ^a	25.20±0.20 ^a	51.87±0.20 ^c	57.27±0.40 ^a	5.69±0.09 ^b	20.79±0.09 ^b	21.55±0.11 ^b	74.69±0.10 ^d
R _S	5.68±0.03 ^a	1.23±0.03 ^a	4.62 ^a	25.10±0.20 ^a	52.04±0.40 ^c	56.94±0.20 ^a	4.59±0.06 ^a	18.57±0.13 ^a	19.13±0.12 ^a	76.12±0.13 ^e

C- control cookies, E_B- cookies formulated with extract of black pepper, E_S- cookies formulated with extract of small cardamom, R_B- cookies formulated with post-extraction sample matrix of black pepper, R_S- cookies formulated with post-extraction sample matrix of small cardamom

*Values of diameter, thickness, weight, hardness and color parameters of cookies are mean±SD of three independent samples

Different letters in a column indicate significant difference at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 3 Spoilage indices of different cookies at different storage days

Storage days	Spoilage indices of cookies				
	C	E _B	E _S	R _B	R _S
20	0.3703	0.2825	0.2126	0.1766	2.1997
40	0.5104	2.6538	3.1082	1.4033	2.6687
60	2.9736	5.9716	6.0303	4.5537	3.3414
80	7.5380	7.7148	6.6217	6.7920	4.3156
100	15.6680	8.1561	9.8548	11.1769	7.4152
120	16.7971	8.8090	13.5992	12.4228	9.8112
140	15.8249	13.8211	15.5626	20.4577	15.9160
160	16.9943	13.5404	14.0392	28.6597	18.4899
180	18.0813	18.0509	14.3634	41.7037	20.6033
200	20.2187	20.5565	15.2153	49.8935	32.2798
Rancid 1 day	14.9807	55.8281	30.0843	40.1788	16.9719
Rancid 2 days	24.4412	68.2221	44.7270	48.7485	21.3886
Rancid 3 days	44.4147	74.2565	53.5389	64.1653	29.8333
Rancid 6 days	67.6875	65.1785	73.5434	82.2783	36.3322
Rancid 10 days	82.1595	74.1129	82.3444	84.4138	44.1959
Rancid 17 days	93.6358	86.5964	90.5616	89.3234	62.2719

C- control cookies, E_B- cookies formulated with extract of black pepper, E_S- cookies formulated with extract of small cardamom, R_B- cookies formulated with post-extraction sample matrix of black pepper, R_S- cookies formulated with post-extraction sample matrix of small cardamom

Table 4 Regression equations generated from conventional biochemical parameters of rancidity and spoilage indices (SI) of different types of cookies stored for 200 days

Sample	Equation	r value	Equation number
C	$FFA = 0.056 \times SI_C + 0.529$	0.858	3
	$PV = 0.611 \times SI_C + 4.073$	0.954	4
	$MDA = 0.162 \times SI_C + 0.219$	0.983	5
E _B	$FFA = 0.014 \times SI_{EB} + 0.431$	0.916	6
	$PV = 0.168 \times SI_{EB} + 1.511$	0.944	7
	$MDA = 0.025 \times SI_{EB} + 0.009$	0.991	8
E _S	$FFA = 0.038 \times SI_{ES} + 0.439$	0.933	9
	$PV = 0.327 \times SI_{ES} + 1.429$	0.889	10
	$MDA = 0.055 \times SI_{ES} - 0.107$	0.907	11
R _B	$FFA = 0.016 \times SI_{RB} + 0.499$	0.981	12
	$PV = 0.186 \times SI_{RB} + 1.695$	0.992	13
	$MDA = 0.048 \times SI_{RB} - 0.007$	0.990	14
R _S	$FFA = 0.033 \times SI_{RS} + 0.597$	0.927	15
	$PV = 0.376 \times SI_{RS} + 3.713$	0.948	16
	$MDA = 0.109 \times SI_{RS} + 0.147$	0.989	17

C- control cookies, E_B- cookies formulated with extract of black pepper, E_S- cookies formulated with extract of small cardamom, R_B- cookies formulated with post-extraction sample matrix of black pepper, R_S- cookies formulated with post-extraction sample matrix of small cardamom